

Studies on bioleaching of silica from Indian chromite ore by a silica tolerant *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀ : Characterisation of some physical parameters and scanning electron microscopic studies

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Abstract : The bioleaching of silica from chromite ore was studied to remove silica from low grade chromite ore and therefore increase the percentage of chromium in the ore. Three microorganisms *Bacillus circulans*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Aspergillus niger* were used for bioleaching studies. The results showed that *Aspergillus niger* has higher potency of silica bioleaching (30%) from chromite ore, followed by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (20.3%) and *Bacillus circulans* (17.8%). The organisms were then grown in their respective growth media along with silica for development of silica tolerant strain. The silica adapted organisms were used for bioleaching studies. Silica tolerant *Aspergillus niger* grown with 90 mg/100 ml silica concentration in the growth media showed maximum bioleaching of silica (53%) from chromite ore. It was named *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀ and selected for further studies. The structural changes in the ore after bioleaching was studied along with morphological changes in *Aspergillus niger* during the process of bioleaching by scanning electron microscope. Physical parameters are optimized for proper cellular growth and effective silica bioleaching from chromite ore. The optimized bioleaching process was carried out at 33 °C for 7 days with 6 ml inoculum having 1.5×10^6 spores/ml. The initial pH of the fermentation media was maintained at 4.5.

Keywords : Chromite ore, silica bioleaching, *Aspergillus niger*, scanning electron microscopic analysis, physical factors.

Introduction

Chromite is an important ore of chromium having 40 to 60% chromium, 2.5 to 8.0% silica along with some other elements. It is mainly used in the manufacture of ferrochrome, chromium metal. It is directly used in steel production as raw material and has significant refractory properties.

Reserves of high grade chromite ores are diminishing due to rapid increase in demands for chromium. Removal of impurities like silica from low grade ore would increase the percentage of chromium in the ore which would convert them to a high grade quality. Using physico-chemical methods for this process are expensive and not eco-friendly. Bioleaching is considered as a promising solution to this problem.

Bacteria plays an important role in silica bioleaching from ore¹⁻⁵. Fungal activity has also been reported to release metallic and silicate ions from minerals and rocks⁶. Many reports have described silica solubilization by fun-

gus to increase the quality of the material by removing silica from it⁷. Poorly ordered lattices are more susceptible to microbial corrosion than well ordered structures of the ore⁸. It has been reported that microbes utilize the carbon source in the medium and secretes 2-ketogluconic acids⁹. The H⁺ ions are able to solubilize silica from ore in the form of silicic acid. Microorganisms adapted to an element previously during its growth has higher potential of bioleaching of the element from ore¹⁰. But a high concentration of silica has an inhibitory role on the growth and bioleaching capacity of the organism.

The present study is carried on development of silica tolerant strain grown at an optimum silica containing growth media which have a high potential of silica bioleaching from ore. Different physical parameters are studied to optimize and increase the bioleaching process as the effectiveness of silica bioleaching largely depends on some physical parameters which regulate the growth and metabolism of the organism as well as efficiency of

bioleaching¹¹. Scanning electron microscopic studies of the organism and ore gives an idea of the morphological changes associated with the bioleaching studies^{12,13}.

Materials and methods :

Chromite ore used for bioleaching studies was obtained from the Sukinda Valley, Orissa, India.

Three microorganisms *Bacillus circulans*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Aspergillus niger* used for bioleaching studies were taken from the laboratory stock culture of Chemical Engineering Department, University of Calcutta. The cultures were previously isolated from the soil of North Bengal and selected for bioleaching studies by senior author.

Medium and conditions for growth : For *Bacillus circulans* : glucose 1%, peptone 0.5%, yeast extract 0.2%, beef extract 0.1%, NaCl 0.5%, Agar 4% (pH 7.0). The organism was incubated for 24 h at 37 °C. For *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* : glucose 1%, peptone 0.5%, yeast extract 0.5%, Agar 4% (pH 5.0). The organism was incubated for 48 h at 30 °C. For *Aspergillus niger* : glucose 10%, KH₂PO₄ 0.1%, NaNO₃ 0.2%, KCl 0.05%, MgSO₄.7H₂O 0.05%, Agar 4% (pH 5.0). The organism was incubated for 7 days at 30 °C. The cultures were then stored at 4 °C and sub cultured during the experiments.

Estimation of silica content in chromite ore : 0.5 g of crushed chromite ore (200 mesh size) was digested with 1 : 1 HCl and baked. It was then dissolved in diluted acid and filtered through Whatman 40 filter paper. The residue was washed with hot water to make it chlorine free. The residue was fired at 800 °C along with filter paper in muffle furnace for 1 h and weighed. It was then treated with HF and conc. H₂SO₄, fired for 15 min at 800 °C and again weighed. The quantity of silica was determined by the difference in weight.

Bioleaching experiment : Bioleaching studies were carried out with 3 microorganisms, each in 100 ml Erlenmeyer flask in sterile condition having 0.3 g ore and 25 ml fermentation media (broth media) for the respective organisms. 5 ml inoculum of *Bacillus circulans* was added to 1st flask and incubated for 48 h at 37 °C, 5 ml inoculum of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* was added to 2nd flask and incubated for 48 h at 30 °C and 5 ml inoculum of *Aspergillus niger* was added to 3rd flask and incubated for 7 days at 30 °C. After bioleaching, the fermentation

media was filtered and the percentage of silica in the filtrate was estimated by silica-molybdate method¹⁴.

Slant media of the 3 respective microorganism was made along with different concentration of silica in mg/100 ml [10,20,30,40,50,60,70,80,90,100,110,120]. The organisms were allowed to grow in different silica containing respective media. With the silica adapted microorganisms bioleaching studies were again carried out.

Scanning electron microscopic studies : The structural changes in the ore before and after bioleaching was observed using Scanning electron microscope. Surface structure of the samples were visualized by LED detectors of the FEI QUANTA Scanning electron microscope (Model no. 200 MK2).

Optimization of physical parameters : The organism having maximum bioleaching potency was selected for further studies. To optimize the initial pH of the fermentation media, experiments were performed with fermentation media having initial pH 3.0, 3.5, 4.0, 4.5, 5.0, 5.5, 6.0. The pH was measured by pH meter and adjusted with 1 (N) HCl and 1 (N) NaOH. To study the time period of fermentation required for bioleaching, experiments were conducted from 6 to 10 days. To study the volume of fermentation media required for bioleaching, experiments were performed with 25, 30, 35, 40 ml media. To optimize the temperature required for bioleaching, the fermentation media were incubated at 27, 30, 33, 37 °C. To find the optimum volume of inoculum and optimum age of inoculum required for bioleaching, experiments were performed with different volume of inoculum (2 to 8 ml) and with different aged cultures incubated for 6 to 10 days respectively. Inoculum used for the study contain spore suspension of 1.5 × 10⁶ spores/ml. After each experiment, cellular growth of the organism was obtained by separating out the cell mat from fermentation media in a filter paper, dried in 110 °C and then weighed.

Results and discussion

Selection of organism and development of silica tolerant *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀ : Among the 3 organisms used for bioleaching studies, it was found that maximum bioleaching of silica from chromite ore was obtained using *Aspergillus niger* (30%) followed by *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (20.3%) and least by *Bacillus circulans* (17.8%) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Percentage of silica bioleaching from chromite ore by *B. circulans*, *S. cerevisiae* and *A. niger* adapted previously in different silica concentration.

The better bioleaching potency of *Aspergillus niger* may be due to release of some specific enzymes from the cell which is able to convert glucose into organic acids in high amount compared to *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Bacillus circulans*. The release of H⁺ ion in the fermentation media is inferred from fall in pH of the media after

bioleaching.

Like mother culture, the silica tolerant *Aspergillus niger* has higher efficiency of silica bioleaching than silica tolerant *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and silica tolerant *Bacillus circulans*. From Fig. 1 it was found that with increase

Fig. A. Scanning electron micrograph of native chromite ore.

Fig. B. Scanning electron micrograph of chromite ore after bioleaching of silica.

Fig. 2. Effect of initial pH of the fermentation media on bioleaching of silica from chromite ore.

in silica concentration, the percentage of silica bioleaching increased. At 90 mg/100 ml silica concentration in the growth media, percentage of silica bioleaching was maximum (53.22%). This may be due to the fact, that micro-organisms adapted to silica during its growth may increase silica solubilization from ore. With further increase

Fig. 3. Effect of time period of fermentation on bioleaching of silica from chromite ore.

in silica concentration in the growth media, bioleaching gradually decreased. *Aspergillus niger* grown with 90 mg/100 ml silica concentration in the growth media was given the name *Aspergillus niger* AB₂₀₀ and used for further studies.

Scanning electron microscopic study of chromite ore : The SEM study of original chromite ore shows the pres-

Fig. 4. Effect of volume of fermentation media on bioleaching of silica from chromite ore.

Fig. 5. Effect of temperature on bioleaching of silica from chromite ore.

Fig. 6. Effect of volume of inoculum on bioleaching of silica from chromite ore.

Fig. 7. Effect of age of inoculum on bioleaching of silica from chromite ore.

ence of quartz, silica and Fe_2O_3 (Fig. A) and due to this the surface of the ore is quite rough. But the SEM of the bioleached ore (Fig. B) shows that the surface of the ore particles becomes quite smooth and there are some grooves formed on the particle which strongly support the ejection of quartz, silica and Fe_2O_3 from chromite ore by

microbial treatment. Again the surface of the leached ore particles emit bright glow due to electron transmission occurring easily from the smooth surface of the leached ore.

Optimised physical parameters : Fig. 2 indicates that with increase in pH of the fermentation media, growth of the organism increased. Maximum growth was obtained with pH 5.0 above which the growth remained constant. Maximum bioleaching was obtained at pH 4.5 which indicates that although growth is influenced by pH, every enzyme has an optimum pH for its activity independent of growth. From Figs. 3 to 7 it can be concluded that with the increase in cellular growth of the organism, bioleaching of silica from ore also increased during the study of different physical parameters. But beyond a certain limit, there was no further increase in growth of the organism along with fall in bioleaching capacity.

From the present investigation, the following optimum cultural conditions are obtained : initial pH of the fermentation media, 4.5; time period of fermentation, 7 days; volume of fermentation media, 30 ml; temperature of fermentation, 33 °C; volume of inoculum, 6 ml and age of inoculum, 7 days.

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